

Effect of Workplace Spirituality Paradigm on Students Achievement

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Abstract

Workplace spirituality attributes the capacity of acceptance of employee inner life nourishment by purposeful work occurs for the benefit of a community (Sandhu, 2015). The major objective of this articulation was to examine the effect of workplace spirituality paradigm on students' achievement at public and private schools of Punjab, Pakistan. The research study was quantitative in nature, descriptive and survey technique was imposed to collect data. The sample of this research study was comprised of 270 participants of public and private schools of the division Sahiwal located in central Punjab. A self-developed questionnaire based on workplace spirituality parameters validated in respect of senior educational expert discussion and piloted before actual data survey. The student's achievement is accessed from the result gazette notification 2017 of eight class conducted by Punjab Examination Commission. The parameters of workplace spirituality like the climate of mutual trust and sense of joy had a direct bearing on public schools students achievement whereas values and worth and goals and objectives had a positive effect on private schools students achievement. Multiple regression analysis was run which shows that workplace spirituality paradigm contributed significantly about 10.8% towards public school student achievement and 10.1% significantly influenced private school students achievement.

Keywords: *Students achievement, multiple regression, workplace spirituality, public schools, influenced, dimensions.*

Introduction

Giacalone & Jurkiewicz (2003) defined workplace spirituality as “it is a framework of organizational values evidenced in the culture that promotes employees' experience of transcendence through the work process, facilitating their sense of being connected to others in a way that provided feelings of completeness and joy.”

The term workplace spirituality is the totality of meaningful work, the pleasure of society and experience value of the institution. Workplace spirituality parameters have a significant influence on workplace satisfaction. The enhanced level of communication channels is flourished in the teaching staff with the linking of the promotion of workplace spirituality criteria (Hassan, Nadeem & Akhter, 2016). Schutte (2016) pointed out that workplace spirituality is a definite postmodern trend, tool and a process taken seriously in business and leadership development. The term workplace spirituality describes a sense of pleasure among employees to remain together in their work with patience, giving direction, association and attached at work. The business related profit concerned organizations have employed to ponder upon workplace spirituality to enhance their financial outcomes by making a vacant hole for pragmatic spiritual practices whereas ontological explanation considers spirituality is an asset for producing a profit (Gocen & Ozgan, 2018). Vasconcelos (2011) portrayed that a large number of theoretical associations found between the societal marketing concept (SMC) and spirituality in the workplace (SWP) theory. Dent et al. (2005) investigated the previous literature about workplace spirituality and indicated seven measures such as; “tied to religion, epiphany, teachable, individual development, measurable, productive/profitable, nature of the phenomenon.” The validity of various parameters of spirituality at work and also predictive validity of these parameters correlate with a large number of working individuals' behaviours (Milliman, Andrew & Ferguson, 2003). Kochukalam, & Srampickal (2018) conceptualizing the workplace spirituality via related literature review and chalk out a preliminary model to explain the variables includes to the workplace spirituality. The major influences put in the context of controlling workplace spirituality are captured at a conceptual level for further description and substantiation.

Rego, & Cunha, (2007) pointed out the impact of dimensions of workplace spirituality like a team, sense of community, linking with organizational values, sense of contribution to society, enjoy at work, the choice for

inner life on different commitment type. Doorgapersad (2017) hypothesized that workplace spirituality increases the working people wellness and had a positive effect on enhanced productivity as well as workplace spirituality influences differently on male and female working individuals (gendered perspective) and will lead to increased productivity. The researcher chalk out a model called workplace spirituality for gender based productivity for an explanation under the roof of existing employee work wellness programmes.

Ahmad and Omar (2016) described the different parameters of spirituality like meaningfulness in work, positive awareness of society and connectedness of working individuals' social values with organizational value. Workplace spirituality is the sum of the inner part and reflects as a general statement of the organizational commitment. The working staff is considered the most important component of any institution. The major emphasis of this articulation was to "establish the effect of workplace spirituality on organizational commitment of academic staff" while the data analysis by using correlation and regression method indicated that a significant positive association is met in the workplace spirituality and organizational commitment. The workplace spirituality had a significant positive influence on job commitments which ultimately leads to enhanced institutional outcomes. The variables like gender, stream, age, and rank also have a positive impact on job performance (Campbell & Hwa, 2014).

The objective of the study - The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of workplace spirituality on students' achievement.

Research question - What is the effect of workplace spirituality on students' achievement?

Methods and Procedure of the Study

The research study was quantitative, descriptive based on survey approach. All the elementary school's teachers were the target population of province Punjab. Punjab is called the land of five rivers. The province of Punjab has divided into nine divisions administratively. The researcher selected Sahiwal division fall in central Punjab. The division Sahiwal consists of three districts, i.e., Pakpattan, Sahiwal and Okara. The researchers selected those fifteen (15) secondary level public and private schools which take an examination under the supervision of Punjab Examination Commission from each district of Sahiwal division. Three (3) elementary school teachers from each public and private school which teach eight classes were selected on a random basis from ninety (90) secondary schools. Therefore, the sample was composed of 270 elementary school teachers from the public and private schools. The questionnaire comprised of seventeen statements linking to measures of workplace spirituality was self-developed as an instrument of the study. The research study tool was piloted in that school which was not included in the sample before actual data collection and validity was also processed through the opinion of best known educational experts before data survey. The results of eight class of selected school were taken from the internet. The student's achievement is accessed by the taken average result of eight class gazette notification 2017 conducted by Punjab Examination Commission.

Presentation and Analysis of Results

Regression Analysis for Public School -For the model with dependent variable students achievement and the independent variables (measures of workplace spirituality paradigms) are predictors of the students' achievement.

Table: 1 Multiple Regression Model for Public Schools to Examine the Effect of Workplace Paradigm on Students Achievement.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson	
1	0.329	0.108	0.048	32.4550	1.688	
Multiple Regression Analysis Of Variance ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Regression	32139.979	17	1890.587	1.795	0.029	
Residual	265438.170	252	1053.326			
Total	297578.150	269				

The value of R (0.329) showed the correlation between the dependent variable and independent variable. The goodness of fit tested and reported by the value of R square. A model would fit the data well if the difference between the observed value and the model predicted value is small. The value of R square ranges

from 0.00 to 1.00, where 0.00 means no variance explained by the explanatory variables and value 1.00 means 100% variance explained by the independent variables. The value of the coefficient of determination R square was .108, which was low. The value of R square provides an estimate of the strength of the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables. The low value of R square did not provide formal research questions testing. Therefore, F- statistics were reported, which was 1.795, and the value of 'p' is .029. The 'p' value shows the group of explanatory variables had a statistically significant relationship with dependent variables.

Linear regression analysis of variance ANOVAs significance described the overall fitness of the model, and it must be less than 0.05 on 95% of confidence interval. The value of $p=.029$ showed that the model was significant and fit as per results. It was concluded that the linear regression model showed 10.8% significance of the set of independent variables, the remaining explanation of 89.2% from other external factors which are not included in the study. The value of Durbin Watson is 1.688, which indicates that data is not auto-correlated. According to Rule of Thumb, if the test statistic value in the range of 1.5 to 2.5 is relatively normal.

Table: 2 Multiple Regression Analysis of Coefficients and Residual Statistics

Measures of Workplace Spirituality	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	298.806	15.154		19.718	.000
1.Meaningful work	2.809	3.266	.099	.860	.391
2.Job Satisfaction	.418	2.865	.013	.146	.884
3.Work connectedness	-5.851	3.309	-.216	-1.769	.078
4.Values and worth	4.682	3.081	.154	1.520	.130
5.Climate of mutual trust and respect	8.937	2.941	.257	3.039	.003
6.Discipline	.862	2.475	.026	.348	.728
7.Priority of caring	1.709	2.153	.054	.794	.428
8.Sense of humanity	-.088	2.635	-.003	-.033	.973
9.Work and social goodness	-.537	2.893	-.016	-.186	.853
10.Creativeness of spirit	2.232	2.275	.080	.981	.327
11. Staff support	.450	2.900	.014	.155	.877
12.Job pressure reduction	4.181	3.183	.109	1.313	.190
13.The institution as a family	2.325	3.410	.081	.682	.496
14.Increase energy value and spirit	-5.716	4.031	-.152	-1.418	.157
15.Goals and objectives	3.435	3.698	.100	.929	.354
16.Happiness	-6.415	3.178	-.196	-2.018	.045
17.Sense of joy	6.662	2.327	.208	2.862	.005
Residuals Statistics					
Model	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Predicted Value	282.225	341.764	307.032	10.9307	270
Residual	-80.8062	95.2441	.0000	31.4127	270
Std. Predicted Value	-2.270	3.177	.000	1.000	270
Std. Residual	-2.490	2.935	.000	.968	270

The values in the analysis are standard errors of the estimators of the measures of workplace spirituality. Actually, the coefficient portrays the relationship of individual independent variables with dependent variables. The combined effect of independent variables was reflected by the intercept of the model which accounts the value 298.806 significantly.

The above table 2 shows that measures of workplace spirituality like the climate of mutual trust and respect and sense of joy had a positive effect on students' achievement. The beta value of climate of mutual trust and respect is 0.257 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to increase of 25.7% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. The beta value of a sense of joy is 0.208 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to an increase of 20.8% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. However, there exists a positive relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this association is statistically significant. The above table shows that independent variable like work connectedness had a negative effect on students achievement. The beta value of work connectedness is -.216 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to decreases of 21.6% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. However, there exists a negative relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this association is statistically significant.

The above table shows that the dimensions of workplace spirituality like meaningful work, job satisfaction, values and worth, discipline, priority of caring, creativeness of spirit, staff support, job pressure reduction, institution as a family and goals and objectives had a positive effect on students achievement. It reflects that a unit increase in these variables will enhance the students' achievement. However, there exists a positive relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality paradigms and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this relation is statistically insignificant.

The table also shows that sense of humanity, work, and social goodness, increase energy value and spirit and happiness had negatively effect on students' achievement. It reflects that a unit increase in these variables will reduce the students' achievement. However, there exists a negative relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality paradigms and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this relation is statistically insignificant.

Regression Analysis for Private School

For the model with dependent variable students achievement and the independent variables (measures of workplace spirituality paradigms) are predictors of the students' achievement.

Table: 3 Multiple Regression Model for Private Schools to Examine the Effect of Workplace Paradigm on Students Achievement.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson
1	0.318	0.101	0.041	36.69952	1.517

Multiple Regression Analyses Of Variance ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	38234.809	17	2249.106	1.670	0.04
Residual	339407.328	252	1346.854		
Total	377642.137	269			

From the above table, the value of R (0.318) shows the correlation between the dependent variable and independent variable. The goodness of fit tested and reported by the value of R square. A model would fit the data well if the difference between the observed value and the model predicted value is small. The value of R

square ranges from 0.00 to 1.00, where 0.00 means no variance explained by the explanatory variables and value 1.00 means 100% variance explained by the independent variables. The value of the coefficient of determination R square is .101, which is low. The value of R square provides an estimate of the strength of the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables. The low value of R square did not provide formal research questions testing. Therefore, F- statistics were reported, which is 1.670, and the value of 'p' is .04. The 'p' value shows the group of explanatory variables had a statistically significant relationship with dependent variables. Linear regression analysis of variance ANOVAs significance describes the overall fitness of the model, and it must be less than 0.05 on 95% of confidence interval. The value of $p=0.04$ showed that the model is significant and fit as per results. It was concluded that the multiple regression model shows 10.1% significance of the set of independent variables, the remaining explanation of 89.9% is from other external factors which are not included in the study.

The table 3 shows that the value of Durbin Watson 1.517 for regression model lies in the range, which indicates that data is not auto-correlated and the residuals are independent. According to Rule of Thumb, if the test statistic value in the range of 1.5 to 2.5 is relatively normal (Chatterjee & Hadi, 2006).

Table: 4 Multiple Regression Analysis of Coefficients and Residual Statistics

Measures of Workplace Spirituality	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	303.820	19.819		15.330	.000
1.Meaningful work	-1.068	2.338	-.033	-.457	.648
2.Job Satisfaction	-.449	2.271	-.013	-.198	.843
3.Work connectedness	-2.468	2.502	-.070	-.987	.325
4.Values and worth	5.056	2.260	.148	2.237	.026
5.Climate of mutual trust and respect	2.974	2.423	.096	1.227	.221
6.Discipline	-7.858	2.575	-.224	-3.052	.003
7.Priority of caring	2.642	3.279	.065	.806	.421
8.Sense of humanity	2.764	3.002	.079	.921	.358
9.Work and social goodness	-2.423	2.466	-.079	-.983	.327
10.Creativeness of spirit	2.322	3.030	.062	.766	.444
11.Staff support	1.652	3.119	.040	.530	.597
12.Job pressure reduction	-5.155	2.982	-.134	-1.729	.085
13.The institution as a family	2.669	3.024	.070	.883	.378
14.Increase energy value and spirit	-.773	2.256	-.026	-.343	.732
15.Goals and objectives	3.880	2.254	.117	1.721	.086
16.Happiness	2.154	2.507	.066	.859	.391
17.Sense of joy	.341	2.623	.010	.130	.897

Residuals Statistics					
Model	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	290.8594	363.1986	324.8626	11.92212	270
Residual	-91.24666	89.69165	.00000	35.52094	270
Std. Predicted Value	-2.852	3.216	.000	1.000	270
Std. Residual	-2.486	2.444	.000	.968	270

The values in the analysis are standard errors of the estimators of the measures of workplace spirituality paradigm. Actually, the coefficient indicates the relationship of individual independent variables with dependent variables. The combined effect of independent variables was reflected by the intercept of the model which originates the value 303.820 significantly.

The above table 4 shows that list of workplace spirituality dimensions like values and worth, and goals and objectives had a positive effect on students' achievement. The beta value of values and worth is 0.148 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to increase of 14.8% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. The beta value of goals and objectives is 0.117 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to increase of 11.7% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. However, there exists a positive relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this association is statistically significant.

The above table shows that independent variable like discipline and job pressure reduction had a negative effect on students' achievement. The beta value of discipline is -0.224 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to a reduction of 22.4% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. The beta value of job pressure reduction is -0.134 which indicates that a unit increases in these variable will leads to a decrease of 13.4% in the students' achievement at one percent level of significance. However, there exists a negative relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this association is statistically significant.

The above table shows that the dimensions of workplace spirituality like the climate of mutual trust and respect, the priority of caring, sense of humanity, creativeness of spirit, staff support, and the institution as a family, happiness, and sense of joy had a positive effect on students' achievement. It reflects that a unit increase in these variables will promote the students' achievement. However, there exists a positive relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality paradigms and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this relation is statistically insignificant.

The table also portrays that meaningful work, job satisfaction, work connectedness, work, and social goodness and increase energy value and spirit had negatively effect on students' achievement. It reflects that a unit increase in these variables will reduce the students' achievement. However, there exists a negative relationship between these measures of workplace spirituality paradigms and the dependent variable student's achievement while the t-statistics and 'p' values indicate that this relation is statistically insignificant.

Conclusion

The parameters of workplace spirituality like climate of mutual trust and respect, sense of joy, meaningful work, job satisfaction, values and worth, discipline, priority of caring, creativeness of spirit, staff support, job pressure reduction, institution as a family and goals and objectives had positive effect on students achievement learning in public schools. It was also concluded that workplace spirituality measures like values and worth, goals and objectives, the climate of mutual trust and respect, the priority of caring, sense of humanity, creativeness of spirit, staff support, the institution as a family, happiness, and sense of joy had direct bearings on private school students' achievement.

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